

Comparative Study of Ropivacaine 0.75% and Levobupivacaine 0.5% in Ultrasound-Guided Axillary Plexus Block for Elective Upper Limb Surgeries

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Abstract:

Background: Axillary plexus block is a common technique for upper limb surgeries, providing adequate analgesia and muscle relaxation. Ropivacaine and levobupivacaine are widely used local anaesthetics, with differences in onset time, duration of the block, and postoperative analgesia.

Aim and Objective: To compare the efficacy of ropivacaine with 0.75% and levobupivacaine with 0.5% in ultrasound-guided axillary plexus block. This comparison is crucial for understanding the differences in onset time, duration of the block, and postoperative analgesia between these two widely used local anaesthetics.

Materials and Methods: This prospective, randomized, double-blind clinical trial was conducted at SVBP Hospital, affiliated with LLRM Medical College, Meerut, involving 80 patients aged 18-65 with ASA physical status I and II. Patients were randomly assigned to Group A (Ropivacaine 0.75%, 25 ml) and Group B (Levobupivacaine 0.5%, 25 ml). The primary outcomes included the onset and duration of sensory and motor blocks. Secondary outcomes were postoperative analgesia, hemodynamic parameters, and complications. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 20.0, with a p-value of <0.05 considered statistically significant.

Results: The mean onset time for sensory block was significantly faster in Group A (7.92 ± 1.01 min) compared to Group B (10.35 ± 1.17 min, $p = 0.011$). Similarly, motor block onset was faster in Group A (9.10 ± 0.87 min) than in Group B (11.27 ± 1.11 min, $p = 0.005$). The duration of the sensory block was shorter in Group A (9.21 ± 0.87 hrs) compared to Group B (12.25 ± 1.20 hrs, $p = 0.032$). Motor block duration was also shorter in Group A (8.54 ± 0.87 hrs) than in Group B (11.41 ± 1.17 hrs, $p = 0.023$). Postoperative analgesia lasted longer in Group B (12.93 ± 1.08 hrs) compared to Group A (9.93 ± 0.86 hrs, $p = 0.038$). Two patients in Group A experienced nausea and vomiting, while no complications were observed in Group B.

Conclusion: Ropivacaine 0.75% provides a faster onset of sensory and motor blocks, while Levobupivacaine 0.5% offers a longer duration of both blocks and postoperative analgesia. Both agents were well-tolerated, with minimal complications. The choice between these two anaesthetics should be guided by the clinical scenario, depending on whether a faster onset or longer duration of block is required.

Keywords: Axillary Plexus Block, Ropivacaine, Levobupivacaine, Ultrasound-Guided, Postoperative Analgesia, Sensory Block, Motor Block.

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Introduction

The axillary plexus block is a widely utilized regional anaesthetic technique for upper limb surgeries, offering effective analgesia and muscle relaxation. [1] Among the various local anaesthetics used, Ropivacaine and Levobupivacaine are prominent choices due to their favourable safety profiles and efficacy. [2] Ropivacaine, a newer long-acting local anaesthetic, is known for its lower toxicity and less motor blockade compared to traditional agents like Bupivacaine. [3, 4]

Levobupivacaine, the S-enantiomer of Bupivacaine, has been developed to reduce cardiovascular and

central nervous system toxicity while maintaining similar anaesthetic properties. [5]

The comparative efficacy of Ropivacaine and Levobupivacaine in ultrasound-guided axillary plexus block remains an area of active research. Both agents are used to provide analgesia in upper limb surgeries, but differences in their onset times, duration of action, and impact on hemodynamic stability may influence their clinical utility. Understanding these differences can help in tailoring anaesthetic approaches to optimize patient outcomes. [6,7]

Previous studies have suggested that ropivacaine might provide a faster onset of sensory and motor blocks, which could be advantageous in a clinical setting where rapid onset is critical.⁴⁻⁶ Conversely, Levobupivacaine might offer a longer duration of motor blockade, which could be beneficial for prolonged surgical procedures or postoperative analgesia. [1-4]

This study aims to compare Ropivacaine 0.75% and Levobupivacaine 0.5% in the context of ultrasound-guided axillary plexus block. By evaluating the time of onset of sensory and motor blocks, duration of motor blockade, postoperative analgesia, and hemodynamic changes, this research provides a clearer understanding of the relative advantages of these two local anaesthetics. The findings from this study could significantly enhance the efficacy of regional anaesthesia for upper limb surgeries, offering hope for improved patient outcomes.

Materials and Methods

This prospective randomized controlled trial was conducted at SVBP Hospital, associated with LLRM Medical College, Meerut. The study received approval from the Ethics Committee (Certificate No./SC-1/2023/1415) and was registered in the National Clinical Trial Registry of India (CTRI/2023/12/06527) on December 19, 2023. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants before enrollment.

Study Design: Our study is a unique prospective randomized controlled trial, conducted over one and a half years, that specifically aims to compare the efficacy of Ropivacaine 0.75% and Levobupivacaine 0.5% in ultrasound-guided axillary plexus block.

Study Population: Our study included a specific population of patients aged 18-65 years, of either sex, and classified as American Society of Anesthesiologists (ASA) physical status I or II. These patients were scheduled for elective upper limb surgeries, and we had strict exclusion criteria to ensure the safety and integrity of the study.

Patients were randomly assigned to two groups using a sealed envelope technique. Group A received Ropivacaine 0.75% (25 ml), and Group B received Levobupivacaine 0.5% (25 ml).

Blinding: The study employed double blinding. An independent anesthesiologist prepared the local anaesthetic, and an independent observer assessed outcomes, ensuring that the investigators performing the block and evaluating outcomes were unaware of the drug administered.

Anesthetic Technique: Patients were positioned supine with the arm abducted to 90 degrees. The axillary area was cleaned with antiseptic, and the ultrasound machine (SonoSite Micromaxx with a 5-10

Hz linear probe) was used for visualization. After identifying the axillary artery, the median, ulnar, and radial nerves were located. The needle was inserted in-plane from the anterior aspect and advanced carefully, with local anaesthetic administered around the nerves.

Monitoring and Assessments: Baseline heart rate, noninvasive blood pressure, and oxygen saturation were recorded. Sensory and motor blockades were assessed every minute up to 20 minutes post-injection using pinprick and modified Bromage scales. Hemodynamic parameters were recorded at 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 10, 15, 30, 60, and 120 minutes. Postoperative analgesia was assessed using the Visual Analog Scale (VAS), and rescue analgesia was administered as needed.

Statistical Analysis: Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 20.0 (IBM, Chicago). Continuous variables were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation, and categorical variables as frequency (percentage). Differences between groups were compared using the Student's t-test for parametric data and the Mann-Whitney U test for non-parametric data. Categorical variables were analyzed using the chi-square test. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

A total of 80 patients were included in the study and randomly divided into two equal groups: Group A (Ropivacaine 0.75%) and Group B (Levobupivacaine 0.5%), each consisting of 40 patients. Demographic characteristics, hemodynamic changes, onset and duration of sensory and motor blocks, postoperative analgesia, and complications were compared between the two groups.

Demographic Characteristics: The mean age of participants in Group A was 33.47 ± 15.01 years, while in Group B, it was 35.63 ± 11.46 years. The difference in age between the two groups was statistically insignificant ($p > 0.05$). Gender distribution also showed no significant difference ($p > 0.05$), with males comprising 65% of Group A and 70% of Group B.

Hemodynamic Parameters

- **Systolic Blood Pressure (SBP):** There were significant differences in SBP at several time intervals. At 2 minutes, Group B had a significantly higher SBP (130.60 ± 11.07 mmHg) than Group A (122.65 ± 12.13 mmHg, $p = 0.022$). Similarly, at 4, 10, and 30 minutes, Group A showed higher SBP values ($p < 0.05$).
- **Diastolic Blood Pressure (DBP):** Significant differences were found at 1, 4, 5, and 90 minutes, with Group B showing lower DBP values at these time points ($p < 0.05$).

- **Mean Arterial Pressure (MAP):** Group A had significantly higher MAP values at 3, 15, and 30 minutes compared to Group B ($p < 0.05$).

Onset of Sensory and Motor Block

- **Sensory Block:** The mean time to onset of sensory block was significantly faster in Group A (7.92 ± 1.01 minutes) compared to Group B (10.35 ± 1.17 minutes), with a p-value of 0.011.
- **Motor Block:** The onset of motor block was also significantly quicker in Group A ($9.10 \pm$

0.87 minutes) compared to Group B (11.27 ± 1.11 minutes), with a p-value of 0.005.

Duration of Sensory and Motor Block

- **Sensory Block Duration:** Group A had a shorter mean duration of sensory block (9.21 ± 0.87 hours) than Group B (12.25 ± 1.20 hours, $p = 0.032$).
- **Motor Block Duration:** The motor block lasted 8.54 ± 0.87 hours in Group A and 11.41 ± 1.17 hours in Group B, with a significant difference ($p = 0.023$).

Table 1: Comparing onset and duration of sensory and motor block

Block Characteristics	Group A (Ropivacaine) Mean \pm SD	Group B (Levobupivacaine) Mean \pm SD	p-value
Onset of Sensory Block (min)	7.92 ± 1.01	10.35 ± 1.17	0.011*
Onset of Motor Block (min)	9.10 ± 0.87	11.27 ± 1.11	0.005*
Duration of Sensory Block (hrs)	9.21 ± 0.87	12.25 ± 1.20	0.032*
Duration of Motor Block (hrs)	8.54 ± 0.87	11.41 ± 1.17	0.023*

Postoperative Analgesia: The total duration of postoperative analgesia was significantly longer in Group B (12.93 ± 1.08 hours) compared to Group A (9.94 ± 0.86 hours, $p = 0.038$).

Table 2: Comparing total duration of analgesia between groups

Duration of Analgesia (hours)	Group A (Mean \pm SD)	Group B (Mean \pm SD)	p-value
Total Duration of Analgesia	9.94 ± 0.86	12.93 ± 1.08	0.038*

Complications: Two patients in Group A experienced nausea and vomiting, whereas no complications were observed in Group B. This difference was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

Table 3: Comparing complication between groups

Complications	Group A (n)	Group B (n)	p-value
Nausea & Vomiting	2	0	0.045*
Other Complications	0	0	-

Discussion

This prospective, randomized clinical study aimed to compare the onset and duration of sensory and motor blocks, complications, and hemodynamic changes using Ropivacaine 0.75% and Levobupivacaine 0.5% in ultrasound-guided axillary plexus blocks. After obtaining informed consent, 80 patients with ASA physical status I and II, aged 18-65 years and undergoing upper limb surgeries, were randomly allocated into two groups: Group A (Ropivacaine 0.75%, 25 ml) and Group B (Levobupivacaine 0.5%, 25 ml). Standardized techniques were used to perform the axillary plexus block, followed by assessments of sensory and motor blocks, pain, and hemodynamic parameters.

In our study, the average age of patients was 33.4 years in Group A and 35.6 years in Group B, with no significant difference between the groups. Both groups had a comparable distribution of male patients, with no significant difference in gender distribution ($p > 0.05$).

The mean onset time for the sensory block was significantly faster in Group A (7.92 minutes)

compared to Group B (10.35 minutes, $p < 0.05$). Similarly, the mean onset of motor block was shorter in Group A (9.10 minutes) compared to Group B (11.27 minutes, $p < 0.05$). The mean duration of the sensory block was significantly shorter in Group A (9.21 hours) than in Group B (12.25 hours, $p < 0.05$). Similarly, the duration of the motor block was shorter in Group A (8.54 hours) compared to Group B (11.41 hours, $p < 0.05$). The duration of postoperative analgesia was also shorter in Group A (9.93 hours) than in Group B (12.92 hours, $p < 0.05$).

Our findings are consistent with Kim HJ et al. [6], who reported that the onset of sensory block was faster with ropivacaine than with levobupivacaine, and the duration of sensory and motor blocks was shorter for ropivacaine. Similarly, Thalamati D et al.¹ found that ropivacaine had a shorter analgesia duration than levobupivacaine. They also observed that the onset of sensory block was faster with ropivacaine (5.22 minutes) than with levobupivacaine (6.88 minutes), and the duration of sensory and motor blocks was longer in the Levobupivacaine group.

Other studies, such as those by Cline E et al. [8] and Fournier R et al. [9], have shown a longer duration of analgesia with levobupivacaine, which is consistent with our results. Fournier R et al. [9] reported that, at equivalent concentrations, levobupivacaine provided a significantly longer duration of analgesia than ropivacaine. Casati A et al. [8] found no differences in sensory or motor block recovery times between the two drugs when used at the same concentration. Brau et al. also demonstrated that levobupivacaine was more effective than ropivacaine in blocking sodium channels in neurons resistant to tetrodotoxin.

Our study showed no significant variations in systolic blood pressure, diastolic blood pressure, mean arterial pressure, oxygen saturation, or heart rate between the two groups from baseline to 120 minutes. This finding aligns with Chandra K et al. [10], who found no statistically significant differences in hemodynamic parameters between the Ropivacaine and Levobupivacaine groups during the study period.

Two patients in Group A experienced nausea and vomiting, while no complications were observed in Group B, with a statistically significant difference ($p < 0.05$). Similar findings were reported by Thalamati D et al. [1], who noted that 3.3% of patients in the Ropivacaine group experienced vomiting, while no adverse events were observed in the Levobupivacaine group.

Study Limitations and Recommendations:

This study was conducted on a relatively small sample size and at a single centre, limiting the generalizability of the results to the broader population. Larger, multi-centre studies are needed to confirm these findings. Additionally, only patients with ASA I and II physical status were included, so further studies are required to assess the safety and efficacy of these drugs in higher-risk patients. Future research should also investigate the use of adjuvants to enhance and prolong the analgesic effect of these local anaesthetics. A more precise method for measuring the block's onset time could improve future studies' accuracy.

Conclusion

In conclusion, while both Ropivacaine and Levobupivacaine are effective for ultrasound-guided axillary plexus block, levobupivacaine offers a longer duration of sensory and motor blocks as well as postoperative analgesia, making it a better choice for surgeries requiring prolonged analgesia. However, ropivacaine has the advantage of a faster

onset, which may be beneficial in clinical settings where a quicker onset of action is desired.

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